

CONDENSATION PRODUCTS OF BENZYLIDENE-ACETONE WITH SUBSTITUTED THIOUREAS

By M. K. Rout

Several 2-arylamino-4-styryl-thiazoles, prepared by condensation of benzylidene-acetone with substituted thioureas, and their mercurated products have been described. Their bactericidal and fungicidal properties have also been evaluated with a view to examining the effect of styryl group in 4-position of the thiazole nucleus.

In continuation of our investigations on secondary thiazolyl amines and their mercurated products (Pujari and Rout, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953 **75**, 4057; this *Journal*, 1954, **31**, 257; Mahapatra and Rout, *ibid.*, 1953, **30**, 398), the present work describes several 2-arylaminothiazoles having a styryl group in 4-position of the thiazole nucleus. They were prepared by the reaction of benzylidene-acetone with substituted thioureas by the modified method of Rout and Pujari (*loc. cit.*).

Bactericidal and fungicidal activities of the above compounds have been investigated as secondary and tertiary thiazolyl amines themselves are reported to be of considerable therapeutic and biological importance (Erlenmeyer and Muller, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, **28**, 922; Sondern and Breivogel, U.S. Pat. 2,440,730, May, 1948) and some thiazole compounds like Asterol dihydrochloride or 2-mercaptobenzothiazole are well-known fungicides. 2-Arylamino-4:5-dimethylthiazoles have also been reported by Das, Padhi and Rout (*Nature*, 1954, **174**, 516) to possess appreciable fungicidal action.

A study of bactericidal and fungicidal activities of these compounds renders possible evaluation of the effect on these activities of a styryl group in 4-position of the thiazole nucleus and also that of different aryl substituents on the amino group.

Consistent with our earlier findings (this *Journal*, 1954, **31**, 357), mercuration with mercuric acetate gives rise to 2-(acetoxymercuri-arylamino)-4-styryl-thiazoles.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Styryl-2-phenylaminothiazole.—To a mixture of benzylidene-acetone (2.92 g.), phenylthiourea (6 g.) and iodine (5.08 g.) benzene (15 c.c.) was added and the whole heated on a water-bath for about 16 hours. Excess of iodine was removed, the crude product was boiled with water and the hot water extract decanted off. To the residual gummy mass liquor ammonia was added and left overnight. The gum solidified. It was filtered and the solid was crystallised from alcohol, m.p. 83°; yield 64%. (Found: N, 9.8; S 11.2. $C_{17}H_{14}N_2S$ requires N, 10.07; S, 11.5 per cent).

Mercuration of Thiazoles.—A solution of the compound (1 M) in alcohol-acetic acid mixture was added to mercuric acetate (1.3 M), dissolved in water (15 to 20 c.c.) containing 2 or 3 drops of acetic acid. The stirring was continued for about 15 minutes and then left overnight with occasional stirring. It was filtered and purified by repeated washing with hot water and very dilute acetic acid.

TABLE I

Comp. No.	Aryl group.	4-Styryl-9-arylaminothiazoles.				4-Styryl-2-(acetoxymercuro)-arylaminothiazoles.			
		M.P.	Yield.	% Nitrogen. Found. Calc.	% Sulphur. Found. Calc.	Comp. No.	M.P.	Yield.	% Mercury Found. Calc.
1	Phenyl	83°	64%	9.8 10.07	11.2 11.5	13	196°	69%	37.1 37.3
2	<i>o</i> -Tolyl	85°	68	9.2 9.59	10.8 10.95	14	159°	71	35.8 36.2
3	<i>p</i> -Tolyl	170°	65	9.1 9.59	10.6 10.95	15	170°	70	35.9 36.4
4	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	77°	73	8.7 8.92	10.1 10.2	16	160°	75	35.2 35.3
5	<i>m</i> -Chlorophenyl	105°	75	8.6 8.92	10.35 10.2	17	164°	73	34.9 35.3
6	<i>p</i> -Chlorophenyl	85°	76	8.55 8.92	10.3 10.2	18	158°	72	34.8 35.3
7	<i>o</i> -Carboxyphenyl	265°	65	8.60 8.69	10.07 9.94	19	228°	64	34.1 34.5
8	<i>p</i> -Carboxyphenyl	175°	60	8.30 8.69	9.5 9.94	20	208°	65	34.2 34.5
9	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	89°	75	8.51 8.67	10.6 9.9	21	220°	73	34.0 34.4
10	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenyl	170°	73	8.45 8.67	10.1 9.9	22	198°	70	34.1 34.4
11	α -Naphthyl	144°	71	8.32 8.54	9.5 9.7	23	206°	75	33.5 34.1
12	β -Naphthyl	140°	74	8.16 8.54	9.1 9.7	24	195°	78	33.9 34.1

Bactericidal Activity.—The Rideal-Walker drop serial dilution method was used for the study of the comparative antibacterial action. The results of biological tests indicating the maximum effective dilution (M.E.D.) of the compounds at 10 minutes' contact are shown against the compounds in Table II. The temperature was 36°. The test organisms were 24 hours' culture of both gram-positive and gram-negative organisms such as *E. Coli* and *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Fungicidal Tests.—For fungicidal assay, the method of Montgomery and Moore (*J. Pomol. Hort. Sci.*, 1938, 25, 253) with slight modifications has been used. *Alternaria Polanduii* Ayyangar was used as the fungus indicator. All the mercurated and unmercurated thiazoles have been tested. The dilution at which spore germination takes place in spite of the presence of the test material and the percentage of germination corresponding to that dilution are recorded in Table II.

TABLE II

Comp. No.	Antibacterial test.		Fungicidal test.
	M.E.D.		(Dilution below which spore germination does not take place).
	<u>E. Coli.</u>	<u>Staph. aureus.</u>	
1	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 18,000
2	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 15,000
3	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 15,000
4	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 20,000
5	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 18,000
6	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 18,000
7	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 12,000
8	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 12,000
9	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 15,000
10	1: 1,000	1: 1,000	1: 15,000
11	1: 2,000	1: 2,000	1: 30,000
12	1: 2,000	1: 2,000	1: 25,000
13	1:50,000	1:25,000	1: 75,000
14	1:75,000	1:50,000	1:100,000
15	1:75,000	1:50,000	1:100,000
16	1:50,000	1:30,000	1: 75,000
17	1:50,000	1:30,000	1:100,000
18	1:75,000	1:50,000	1:100,000
19	1:25,000	1:10,000	1: 75,000
20	1:25,000	1:10,000	1:100,000
21	1:25,000	1:10,000	1: 75,000
22	1:25,000	1:10,000	1: 75,000
23	1:75,000	1:40,000	1:150,000
24	1:60,000	1:50,000	1:150,000

Thanks are due to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa for research grants to carry out this investigation.

MAYURBHANJ CHEMICAL LABORATORY,
RAVENSHAW COLLEGE,
CUTTACK,

Received September 17, 1955.